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NONSYNCHRONOUS VIBRATIONS CAUSED BY UNSTEADY TIP CLEARANCE FLOW WITH CONSIDERATION OF AERODYNAMIC DAMPING IN A TRANSONIC ROTOR

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ABSTRACT

A transonic single rotor is simulated numerically in this paper to investigate the nonsynchronous vibration (NSV) caused by tip clearance flow (TCF). Unsteady process of TCF is obtained by solving unsteady 3D Reynolds-averaged Navier-Stokes equations, the responses of blade are performed by full/mode-superposition transient dynamic analysis method, and the aerodynamic modal damping ratio (AMDR) is calculated by aeroelastic eigenvalue method with the aerodynamic force of blade vibration separating from that of TCF. Both of single and multiple passages results show that radial vortexes and shedding vortexes generate periodically in every passage due to the unsteady flow of TCF. They propagate in circumferential direction and flow downstream, respectively, and constitute the excitation of NSV. Different from forced response, the excitation generates by the blades themselves and is nonsynchronous with the rotating speed. Different from the flutter, the responses of NSV are dominated by several modes. The torsional and chord modes are easier to be excited, and whatever the operating condition is, relative large vibration stresses always exist at the blade leading edge in tip region, which may cause high cycle fatigue. When the excitation is TCF, no phenomenon of locked-in is triggered, even though the frequencies of TCF and blade vibration are very close. While the excitation frequency matches the natural frequencies, the damping plays an important role in suppressing responses, and therefore, it should be taken into consideration. In additional, if the vibration stresses near resonance demand to be calculated accurately, the frequency errors should also be considered.

INTRODUCTION

The phenomena of aeroelasticity exist widely in aircraft engines. Two main aeroelastic phenomena are

flutter and forced response, which may cause serious vibration problem. Flutter usually occurs at low reduced frequency. It is a self-excited aeroelastic phenomenon and generally nonsynchronous. Forced response is caused by the periodic variation of aerodynamic excitation around circumference and is usually synchronous with the rotating speed. Nonsynchronous vibration (NSV) is different from the two above. It can happen within a single row and the excitations generally come from the tip clearance flow (TCF) or the separation flow from the blade leading edge.

The NSV caused by unsteady TCF is first found by Baumgartner and Kameier [1], named as rotating instabilities (RIs). The excitation is identified by the vortex shedding in blades tip area, which is not in resonance with engine orders. This is also verified by Kielb [2] subsequently. He investigated a transonic stage numerically and experimentally. The results showed that the vibration frequency shifts little (about 2%) with the rotating speed increasing and the amplitude of unsteady pressure is significantly higher in tip area than that due to IGV passing. The same compressor was simulated by Im [3] to analyse the aerodynamic excitation of NSV. He proposed that the structure vibration amplitude is small and has little effect on the aerodynamic force. He also found that the tip clearance size and shape have a significant effect on the frequency and amplitude of the aerodynamic force and further verified that the traveling vortices induce NSV. Mailach [4, 5], Maerz [6], Vo [7], Pardowitz [8, 9] investigated the aerodynamic excitation of NSV at subsonic condition. They all found that the unsteady pressure caused by the motion of TCF only exists in tip area and rises with the tip clearance increasing. It is also worth to say that Zhang and He [10] found the unsteady process of TCF in a turbine stage with the pressure ratio greater than 1 in blade tip area.

Inoue [11-13] experimentally investigated on stall of a low-speed compressor and found the existence of unsteady

oscillation flow, which is caused by the radial vortex forming from the leading edge separation flow. The author named this operating condition as “mild stall condition” and described the radial vortex as “tornado-like separation vortex”. Brandstetter [14] conducted detailed experiment on both transonic and subsonic conditions and found that the radial vortex disturbances are similar for the both conditions and the vibration of blade contributes to the forming of radial vortex in return.

Holzinger [15] and Moeller [16, 17] thought that the NSV is a phenomenon of self-excited rotating instability. Therefore, they specify the blade vibrating at a certain mode and estimate the instability of rotor system with aerodynamic modal damping ratio (AMDR). The results show that the unsteady TCF has a significant effect on the AMDR and sometimes may result a negative value.

Thomassin [18, 19] suggested a theory named jet core feedback to explain the phenomenon of NSV, which is different from the theories above. He thought that when the rotating speed and pitch distance are appropriate, the TCF impinges on the blade tip area of pressure surface and the acoustic feedback would resonate with the unsteady TCF and magnify the amplitude of unsteady pressure. Basing on the theory, Drolet [20] further gave a tip instability convection coefficient to predict the critical rotating speed of NSV.

To the best knowledge of the authors, most of the studies regard the unsteady aerodynamic force as the purely excitation of NSV or the aerodynamic damping part. However, the unsteady aerodynamic force consists of multiple components, such as the wakes from upstream blades row, unsteady pressure due to blades motion, and unsteady TCF or separation flow, which may provide both excitation and aerodynamic damping. Therefore, this paper takes the both aspects into consideration and concentrates on the excitation caused by TCF and the response of NSV with considering AMDR.

NOMENCLATURE

A	influence coefficient matrix
Am	complex amplification factor
C, M, K	damping, mass, stiffness matrix
c	correction factor
f^{VIB}	aerodynamic force on the blade surface due to blade vibration
hn	normalized helicity
Im, Re	imaginary part, real part
s	displacement vector in physical space
\vec{U}	relative velocity vector in flow field
\mathbf{u}	displacement vector in modal space
α, β	multipliers of Rayleigh damping
\mathbf{u}	displacement vector in modal space
$\vec{\zeta}$	vorticity vector
λ	square root of complex eigenvalue of the aeroelastic system
ξ	modal damping ratio
Φ_i	matrix of mass-normalized modal shapes
ω	frequency of excitation
ω_j	modal natural frequency

SUBSCRIPTS

aero	aerodynamic parameters in physical space
i, j	modal orders
mode	parameters in modal space
stru	structural parameters in physical space

METHODOLOGIES

A transonic rotor is investigated here. This study object is simulated under three different operating speeds: 80%, 90% and 100% n . The tip clearance is enlarged to 1.90% tip chord length to motivate the unsteady process of TCF. The design parameters are shown in Table 1.

Table 1 Design parameters of rotor

Parameter	Value
Rotor speed (100% n)	11150rpm
Blade number	31
Radius of rotor leading edge	0.337m
Blade tip chord	0.089m
Inlet hub-to-tip ratio	0.39
Outlet hub-to-tip ratio	0.45
Total pressure ratio	1.49

The movement of blade contributes little to the unsteady characteristic of TCF, which has been verified by Im [3]. Therefore, a decoupling method is utilized here:

- the unsteady flow field is simulated with rigid blade; then the flow field is analysed and the unsteady aerodynamic force is extracted for the response analysis;
- the aerodynamic force extracted is inflicted on the blade surface of the solid mode to calculate the response of the blade system;
- modal analysis of the rotor is done to obtain the natural mode and specify the dominating modal orders;
- AMDRs of the dominating modes are obtained by the method of aeroelastic eigenvalue;
- the responses are recalculated with taking consideration of the AMDRs;
- at last, the influences of AMDRs and frequencies sensitivity on responses are investigated.

The CFD and FEM solvers employed in this paper are called CFX 16.0 and ANSYS 16.0, respectively. The computational grids are shown in Fig. 1. Nodes a to e are the locations where maximum vibration stress may exist.

Fig. 1 Grid systems of CFD (top) and FEM (bottom)

Method of computational fluid mechanics

The 3-D Reynolds averaged Navier-Stokes equations are computed. The equations are discretized using a cell-centered control volume method. High resolution scheme has been adopted for spatial discretization with a special nonlinear recipe at each node [21]. Second order backward Euler scheme is adopted for the transient term. As for turbulence model, the k- ϵ two-equation turbulence model with wall function [22, 23] is used.

For the CFD grids, H-type grid is generated in region of main flow and up/downstream of blade, and O-type grid is generated in region of tip clearance and around blade. Three solutions with different cell numbers are used to perform an evaluation on the sensitivity of grid dimension. As shown in Fig. 2 and 3, the three grid levels perform a similar characteristic, but the coarse grid model results an obvious narrow operating range and a different characteristic with the medium and refined grid model at the left part of the characteristic line. The points in red dashed circles in Fig. 2 share the same boundary condition and are further compared in Fig. 3. The errors are valued basing on the results of refined grid model. It is obvious that the coarse grid model results conspicuous differences with the medium and refined models, which two show a very similar results. At last, the medium grid level is selected for grid dependency. The computational domain is consisted of 144 points streamwise, 41 points pitchwise, and 57 points spanwise including 17 points in tip clearance. The total grids number is about 0.44 million.

Fig. 2 Performance of the transonic rotor at three grid levels

A. Performance parameters VS grid levels

B. Tip flow field of different grid levels

Fig. 3 Errors of three grid levels at the same operating condition

In additional, no-slip and no-heat transfer boundary conditions are applied on the solid walls. The total pressure, total temperature and flow direction are applied at the inlet, and a turbulence intensity value of 5% is specified. At the outlet, the static pressure is specified at the hub, and the radial equilibrium equation is employed to obtain the static pressure from hub to shroud. The flow is assumed to be periodic in the pitchwise direction. Thus, a periodic boundary condition is applied between the two pitchwise direction boundaries of the single passage.

It is worth to note that the CFD computational domain contains a single passage with a direct periodic boundary condition, which can simulate the unsteady process of TCF accurately, but perhaps lead an error on the oscillation

frequency of TCF. Actually, this single passage method eliminates the circumferential uniform of RIs.

Full transient dynamic analysis method

For the FEM model, hexahedron element with 8 nodes is selected. The total number of elements is 2.772 thousand and the minimum jacobian is 0.39. The displacement of the nodes on the blade root surface is constrained to zero. Full transient dynamic analysis is used to obtain the response with the aerodynamic excitation. The Rayleigh damping is applied for the FEM simulation. The modal damping ratios of 1st bending and torsion modes are specified as 0.05% and used to obtain the values of multipliers α and β by formulas 1 and 2. The damping ratios of other modes are calculated basing on the formula 3.

$$C = \alpha M + \beta K$$

$$\alpha = \frac{2\xi_i \omega_j - 2\xi_j \omega_i}{\omega_j^2 - \omega_i^2} \omega_i \omega_j \quad (1)$$

$$\beta = \frac{2\xi_i \omega_i - 2\xi_j \omega_j}{\omega_i^2 - \omega_j^2} \quad (2)$$

$$\xi_i = \frac{\alpha + \beta \omega_i^2}{2\omega_i} \quad (3)$$

where ξ and ω represent modal damping ratio and frequency, respectively. i and j represent different mode orders. The results are shown in Table 3.

Aeroelastic eigenvalue method

Basing on the response analysis, the primary modes contributing to the vibration can be obtained. Then the AMDRs of these modes are calculated by aeroelastic eigenvalue method. The aeroelastic eigenvalue method has been widely used and verified in previous studies, especially for mistuned system analysis. The blades system in this paper is tuned and the eigenvalue method is used to reduce computation cost. Here, a brief description is presented. The vibration equation in physical coordinate without structural damping is as follows:

$$M_{stru} \ddot{s} + K_{stru} s = f_{aero}^{VIB} \quad (4)$$

where f_{aero}^{VIB} is the aerodynamic excitation relative to vibration. The matrixes and vectors in equation 4 can be translated into modal space by formula 5 to 8:

$$s = \Phi_l u \quad (5)$$

$$M_{mode} = \Phi_l^T M_{stru} \Phi_l \quad (6)$$

$$K_{mode} = \Phi_l^T K_{stru} \Phi_l \quad (7)$$

$$f_{mode}^{VIB} = \Phi_l^T f_{aero}^{VIB} \quad (8)$$

Assuming that the unsteady aerodynamic force satisfies the linear superposition principle, then by introducing the influence coefficient matrix A , the aerodynamic force vector in modal space can be expressed as

$$f_{mode}^{VIB} = A u \quad (9)$$

By premultiply Φ_l^T and substituting formula 5 to 9 into equation 4, we get

$$(A - K_{mode}) u = M_{mode} \ddot{u} \quad (10)$$

In modal space, the vibration is assumed to be harmonic. Therefore, the displacement can be written as

$$u = \bar{u} e^{\lambda t} \quad (11)$$

where \bar{u} is the complex amplitude of displacement u . While Φ_l is mass-normalized modal shapes, the mass and stiffness matrix in modal space can be expressed as

$$M_{mode} = E \quad (12)$$

$$K_{mode} = \Omega \quad (13)$$

where E and Ω are the unit matrix and diagonal matrix containing the square of the blade nature frequency as its diagonal elements. By substituting formula 11 to 13 into equation 10, we get

$$(A - \Omega) \bar{u} = \lambda^2 \bar{u} \quad (14)$$

where λ is the square root of complex eigenvalue of the aeroelastic system and the real part of λ represents the damping term. The aeroelastic instability can be expressed as

$$\text{Re}(\lambda) \geq 0 \quad (15)$$

Then, the AMDR can be calculated as follows:

$$\xi = -\frac{\text{Re}(\lambda)}{\text{Im}(\lambda)} \quad (16)$$

Mode-superposition transient dynamic analysis method

In order to consider the influence of AMDRs, mode-superposition transient dynamic analysis method is further utilized to obtain the response under the aerodynamic excitation. In this method, the responses are obtained by superimposing the individual modal responses, which can be described as follows:

$$\{s\} = \sum_{i=1}^n \{\Phi_i\} u_i \quad (17)$$

where n is the selected modal orders. In order to obtain the exact solution, all the modal order contributing to the response should be considered. For the NSV investigated in this paper, the results with the first six, the first ten, the first twenty and the first forty modal shapes are compared. It is found that the result of the considering the first six modal shapes case is different from the other cases and the results of the last three cases are almost the same, which means that considering the first ten modal shapes is enough.

When executes the transient dynamic analysis, the time step size is set equal to the time step of the calculation of the unsteady flow field. The convergence histories of the unsteady flow field calculation and the responses of the blade are shown in Fig. 4.

Fig. 4 Convergence histories of monitor points (flow field: top, solid: bottom)

RESULTS

The performances of the rotor with different rotating speeds are shown in Fig. 5. The mass flow is dimensioned by the maximum mass flow of single passage simulation at the design rotating speed (100%*n*). It can be seen that the simulation results can't reflect the decreasing of pressure ratio, but they are generally consistent with the experimental results. The difference is mainly caused by the enlargement of the tip clearance. The discrete red and blue points are the solutions of the unsteady 3D RANS equations. The unsteady processes of TCF appear at the rotating speeds of 90% and 100%*n*, which are marked by Points 1 to 5. Due to the oscillation of TCF, the results are a little different between steady and unsteady simulation.

Fig. 5 Performances of the transonic rotor with different operation conditions

Unsteady process of the tip flow field

The unsteady process of tip clearance vortex (TCV) in tip flow field of Point 2 is shown in Fig. 6. The normalized helicity Hn is used to measure the relationship between the vorticity $\vec{\zeta}$ and velocity \vec{U} , which is defined as:

$$\vec{\zeta} = \vec{\nabla} \times \vec{U} \quad (17)$$

$$Hn = \frac{\vec{\zeta} \cdot \vec{U}}{|\vec{\zeta}| |\vec{U}|} \quad (18)$$

The normalized helicity Hn represents the cosine of vortex and velocity. Therefore, $|Hn|=1$ represents that the trajectory of vortex cores is consistent with the main flow which means that the TCV maintain a complete structure. If the Hn is approximately zero, this signifies that the TCV breaks down.

It can be seen that a radial vortex forms in passage and impacts on the tip leading edge of the following blade within an oscillation period. At the same time, with the radial vortex propagating around circumference, part of the blockage falls off the broken TCV, forms a shedding vortex, and then flows downstream along the tip pressure side of blade.

Fig. 6 TCV in tip flow field

The 1st harmonic of the unsteady pressure on blade surfaces are depicted in Fig. 7. The results show that the unsteady processes of different operation conditions are similar. The propagation of radial vortex causes high unsteady pressure amplitude at the blade leading edge of tip pressure surface side and the motion of shedding vortex causes broad band unsteady pressure oscillation. While the vortex sheds downstream, it grows in radial direction. It can also be found in Fig. 7 that with the mass flow decreasing, the impacting point of radial vortex moves upstream and the amplitude and influence area of unsteady pressure enlarge. With the rotating speed decreasing, the oscillation of flow field becomes weak and even disappears. This is because that the aerodynamic load in blade tip region decreases.

Fig. 7 First harmonic of unsteady pressure (P_1) on blade surface (kPa)

The oscillation frequencies of the TCF are listed in Table 2. It can be seen that the oscillating frequency decreases with the mass flow reducing. This is easy to be understood. As analyse above, the oscillation process is consisted of the circumferential propagation of radial vortex and the propagation of shedding vortex along flow direction. While the mass flow reduces, the axial flow velocity becomes smaller, and it takes more time for the shedding vortex to flow downstream and out of the passage, what makes the oscillating period longer. The flow field of Points 1 to 5 show similar unsteady process of TCF.

Table 2 Oscillation frequencies of TCF

Operating condition	Oscillating frequency (Hz)
Point 1	3893
Point 2	3703
Point 3	3355
Point 4	3542
Point 5	3172

Response of the blade under different operating conditions

In this part, the modal analysis is done first to obtain the modal shapes and frequencies. The modal damping ratios of 1st bending and torsion modes are specified as 0.05%. Then, the coefficients α and β of Rayleigh damping matrix can be obtained by formulas 1 and 2. Consequently, the damping ratios of other modes are calculated basing on the formula 3. The frequencies and modal damping ratios of first ten orders are listed in Table 3 (100%n). The major orders are stressed with red colour.

Table 3 Frequencies and damping of different modes

Modal order	Frequency (Hz)	Modal damping ratio
1 (1B)	307.32	0.0005
2	712.38	0.0005
3 (1T)	1000.2	0.000598
4	1532.1	0.000821
5	2287.3	0.001168
6	2599.2	0.001316
7 (1C)	2801.4	0.001412
8	3501.3	0.001747
9	3565.2	0.001778
10	4526.7	0.002243

The modal shapes are further described in Fig. 8. It can be seen that the 7th order mode is the 1st chordwise bending modal shape, the 8th order mode is the 3rd torsional modal shape, and the 9th and 10th order modes are the combination of bending and torsional modal shapes. According to Table 3, although the 1st two modes are specified as 0.05%, the modal damping ratios of the four major modal orders (7th-10th) have enlarge about 3 to 4 times and reach 0.15% to 0.2%.

Circumferential modal displacement:

Circumferential modal stress:

Radial modal stress:

Axial modal stress:

7th mode 8th mode 9th mode 10th mode

Fig. 8 Modal shapes of the rotor blade

Then, the responses of the blade to the unsteady TCF are analysed by full transient dynamic analysis method, and the results are shown in Fig. 9. All the results of the operation conditions show that the axial stresses are smaller than the radial and circumferential stresses and the maximum axial stresses almost unchanged with changing the operating condition. The radial stress and circumferential stress are the primary component, especially in tip region. The radial stresses are larger at about 70% to 80% blade spans and the largest circumferential stress appears at the tip of the blade suction side. The maximal displacement locates at the leading edge of the blade tip. It is worth to note that the constraint conditions may cause stress concentration at the root of blade which won't happen in real structure. This should be taken into consideration during response analysis.

Fig. 9 Response of the blade at different operating conditions

The summary of responses is listed in Table 4 (the modal orders listed in parentheses are secondary). The locations of maximum vibration stress are described in Fig. 1. It can be seen that the responses are mainly contributed by the 8th, 9th and especially 7th modal shapes. Combining the table 2 and 3, it can be seen that the frequency of the 7th mode is farther away from the excitation frequency than the 8th, 9th and 10th mode, but it make a greater contribution to the vibration shape of response in most instances. This indicates that the 7th modal shape is much easier to be excited. It is also should be note that the 10th mode hardly contributes to the responses, even though it is more close to the excitation frequencies than the 7th mode in operating conditions of Points 1 and 2.

Comparing the results of Points 1, 2 and 3, it is obvious that while the rotating speed keeps constant, vibration stresses increase rapidly with the mass flow decreasing. This is because the amplitude of the unsteady pressure enlarges and the oscillation frequency reduces with the mass flow decreasing. While the operation point

changes from Point 2 (100%*n*) to Point 4 (90%*n*), which two points may lie in the same operating line, both of the unsteady pressure amplitude and frequency reduce, but they have an opposite influence on the responses. Therefore, the vibration stresses change little.

Table 4 Response characteristic of blade

Operating condition	Excited modal orders	Maximum vibration stress (MPa) and location	
		Radial	Circumferential
Point 1	7 (8, 9)	0.4 (c)	1.0 (d)
Point 2	7 (8, 9)	1.1 (b)	1.4 (d)
Point 3	8 (9)	11 (a)	7.0 (d)
Point 4	9	0.9 (b)	0.8 (d)
Point 5	7	2.0 (a)	1.2 (e)

Aerodynamic damping ratio of the primary modes

As we know, the damping consists of the structural damping and aerodynamic damping. The structural damping is usually very small without dampers and the aerodynamic damping plays an important role in suppressing or stimulating vibration and the AMDR can vary from several percent to a few ten thousandths or even a negative value while flutter happens. Therefore, the aerodynamic damping should be taken into consideration while investigate the response of blade excited by aerodynamics. The AMDRs of 7th and 8th modes are calculated in this part basing on the aeroelastic eigenvalue method described above. The aeroelastic eigenvalue method has been verified on the same rotor in Ref. [24], and won't be repeated here again.

As shown in Fig. 10, seven passages model is selected in this part. The intermediate blades are specified vibrating as the 7th and 8th modal shapes, respectively. The monitoring points are marked by red dots. The operating condition of Point 2 is recalculated here.

Fig. 10 Model of seven passages

Figure 11 shows the Fourier analysis results of the monitoring points in Fig. 10. The unsteady pressure amplitude induced by blade vibration and the unsteady pressure amplitude of TCV oscillation are depicted in Fig. 12 and 13, respectively. The results from the seven passages model show that:

- the frequency and amplitude of the unsteady pressure of TCF keeps almost constant with the vibration frequency changing, and no

phenomenon of TCF oscillation frequency shifting to the vibration frequency (locked-in) is observed, even when the vibration frequency (8th mode) is very close to the oscillation frequency of TCF;

- the unsteady pressure induced by the vibration of intermediate blade decays rapidly as the distance to the intermediate blade increases;
- both of the unsteady process and frequency of TCF oscillation obtained from the seven passages model are similar to the results of single model, which are shown in Fig. 6 and table 2, respectively.

Fig. 11 Fourier analysis of monitoring points results (operating condition of Point 2)

Fig. 12 Amplitude of unsteady pressure induced by intermediate blade vibration

Fig. 13 Unsteady pressure amplitude of TCV oscillation

The aerodynamic forces induced by blade vibration are extracted and used to calculate the amplitudes and phase angles of the aerodynamic influence coefficients, which are described in Fig. 14. The intermediate blade is marked as blade 0. It can be seen that:

- the aerodynamic influence coefficient amplitudes of the middle three blades are large (the coefficient on the intermediate blade is the largest and the coefficients on the adjacent blades -1 and 1 are also considerable) and the coefficients on blades ± 2 and ± 3 are almost zero, which seems indicate that only the middle three passages should be taken in consideration when calculate the AMDR;
- the results here are different from the conditions of low-order modes, in which the fluctuation of aerodynamic forces induced by blade vibration attenuate slower and propagate farther; therefore, more passages require to be simulated in condition of low-order modes (this is not the focus of this paper);
- the phase angles distribution show that the aerodynamic forces generated by the blade itself have similar influences on the AMDR of 7th and 8th mode, but the aerodynamic forces caused by the adjacent blades have distinctly different effects on the AMDR of 7th and 8th mode;
- the aerodynamic influence coefficient amplitude of 7th mode on the -3 blade increases abnormally, because the vibration unsteady aerodynamic forces are too small to separate from the Doppler shift component of the TCV, but this small component contribute little to the AMDR.

Fig. 14 Aerodynamic influence coefficients distribution

The aerodynamic influence coefficients matrix A is obtained by looping the aerodynamic influence coefficients into the elements in the matrix. Thus, basing on the equations 14 and 16, the AMDRs of the 7th and 8th modes are calculated at different nodal diameters and shown in Fig. 15. The smallest AMDRs of 7th and 8th modes are 0.127% observed at 29th nodal diameter (2nd nodal diameter of the backward traveling wave) and 0.075% obtained at 8th nodal diameter, respectively. Comparing with the values of 7th and 8th modal damping ratios calculated from the Rayleigh damping (shown in table 3), the AMDRs of the 7th and 8th modes are much smaller, especially the 8th mode. If the changing of damping ratios is considered, this perhaps causes more significant vibration.

Fig. 15 AMDRs under different nodal diameters

Effect of the nature frequencies and AMDR on the response

In order to consider the influence of AMDRs, in this part, the operating condition of Point 2 is taken as an example to recalculate the responses by the method of mode-superposition transient dynamic analysis. The first twenty modal shapes are taken into consideration, which is enough to obtain the accurate results of responses. The modal damping ratios are derived from the formula 3 and applied to the corresponding modes. The results are shown in Fig. 16. It can be seen that the displacement and stresses distribution are similar to the results obtained by the full transient dynamic analysis method shown in Fig. 9. Only the circumferential stresses distribution in the tip region of the blade have some differences from the results depicted in Fig. 9, and the maximum radial and axial stresses are a little smaller than before. However, in general, the mode-

superposition transient dynamic analysis method rebuilds satisfied results of the blade responses.

Circumferential displacement and stresses in circumferential, radial and axial directions

Fig. 16 Results obtained by mode-superposition transient dynamic analysis method

Then, the modal damping ratios of 7th and 8th modes are replaced by the minimum AMDRs calculated in the previous part (0.127% of 7th mode and 0.075% of 8th mode). Basing on the new values, the responses are analysed again and the results are shown in Fig. 17. As the figure describes, the responses change little when reduce the modal damping ratios of 7th and 8th modes.

Circumferential displacement and stresses in circumferential, radial and axial directions

Fig. 17 Responses with considering AMDRs

This is because that the frequency of excitation induced by TCV is far away from the natural frequencies at the operating condition of Point 2. The differences between the frequency of excitation and natural mode supply a function of damping, which is more effective than the modal damping ratios themselves.

The responses of different modal orders can be regarded as different single degree of freedom systems in modal space and the total displacement can be approximated by formula 17. Therefore, the complex amplification factor Am of the blade system can be depicted as follows:

$$\text{Re}(Am) = c_0 \sum_{j=1}^n \left[\frac{1 - c_j^2 \bar{\omega}_j^2}{(1 - c_j^2 \bar{\omega}_j^2)^2 + (2c_j \xi_j \bar{\omega}_j)^2} \right] \quad (20)$$

$$\text{Im}(Am) = c_0 \sum_{j=1}^n \left[-\frac{2c_j \xi_j \bar{\omega}_j}{(1 - c_j^2 \bar{\omega}_j^2)^2 + (2c_j \xi_j \bar{\omega}_j)^2} \right] \quad (21)$$

where n is the selected modal orders, ξ_j is the modal damping ratio of j^{th} order and $\bar{\omega}_j$ is the frequency ratio of the excitation and j^{th} natural mode, $\bar{\omega}_j = \omega / \omega_j$. In additional, c_0 and c_j are the correction factors of the modal superimposed approximation and the correction factor of the frequency errors due to Doppler shift or

calculation, respectively. According to formulas 20 and 21, the amplification factor amplitude of the 7th and 8th modal components can be calculated, while ignores the correction factor c_j . The results are listed in Table 5 and are similar with the numerical simulation results above: changing modal damping ratios have little influence on the responses and the differences of the frequency between excitation and natural mode play an important role at the operating condition of Point 2.

Table 5 Amplitude components of the amplification factor A_m with different modal damping ratios

Modal order	Frequency differences	Rayleigh Damping	A_m	AMDR	A_m
7	24.3%	0.141%	1.34	0.127%	1.34
8	5.4%	0.175%	8.43	0.075%	8.44

For further study, the natural frequencies of blade are altered by modifying the elasticity modulus and density. The frequency of 8th mode is adjusted to match the excitation frequency and the results are given in Table 6. It is worth to note that as the adjustment is small, the modal shapes are consistent with the previous ones. In fact, the frequencies of different blades in the same row generally have differences of no more than 5% in the actual structure.

Table 6 Frequencies of different modal orders

Modal order	Frequency (Hz)	
	Before	After adjustment
1 (1B)	307.32	313.42
2	712.38	724.87
3 (1T)	1000.2	1072.0
4	1532.1	1591.1
5	2287.3	2439.7
6	2599.2	2735.1
7 (1C)	2801.4	2953.2
8	3501.3	3702.5
9	3565.2	3744.4
10	4526.7	4754.6

Then, the responses are analysed again once more and the results are shown in Fig. 18 that the vibration stresses are enlarged much more significantly than the results of previous natural frequencies (Fig. 16). The maximum values are increased by four to ten times and the domination modal order changes from 7th combining with 8th and 9th to only 8th, which modal frequency has been adjusted to match the excitation frequency.

Circumferential displacement and stresses in circumferential, radial and axial directions

Fig. 18 Responses with increasing natural frequencies

When the excitation closes to the natural modal frequency, the corresponding modal damping ratio will

play an important role in suppressing responses. The effect of damping is evaluated by formulas 20 and 21, and as the 8th modal frequency is adjusted to match the excitation, only the component of 8th mode should be considered. The results show that:

- the responses are very sensitive to the differences of frequency under the resonance condition; therefore, the errors of frequency c_8 will have a great influence on the response;
- if ignore this error, the responses would be enlarged about 34 times than the results before shown in Table 5, and reducing the modal damping ratio to 0.075% would further double the responses;
- however, the results in Fig. 18 show that the responses only increase by less than ten times; such a big difference can be caused by only 0.5% of frequency errors under the damping conditions shown in Table 7;
- if take the 0.5% errors into consideration ($c_8 = 0.995$), the responses are about 11 times larger than the results in Table 5 after reducing the 8th modal damping ratio to 0.075%.

Table 7 Amplification factor amplitude A_m of the 8th mode with different modal damping ratios

8 th modal damping ratio	A_m (with $c_8=1$)	Multiple of results in Table 5	A_m (with $c_8=0.995$)	Multiple of results in Table 5
0.1747%	282.8	33.55	87.39	10.37
0.075%	627.1	74.30	90.96	10.78

At last, in order to verify the evaluation above, the 8th modal damping ratio of the blade with new natural frequencies is set to 0.075% to recalculate the responses. The displacements and stresses are described in Fig. 19. The legend in Fig. 19 is kept the same with Fig. 18. Comparing the results in Fig. 18 and 19, it can be seen that while adjust the 8th modal frequency matching the excitation, reducing damping ratio has an obvious influence on the responses. The maximum vibration stresses increases about 4.2% to 20% and are about 5 to 12 times that of the values in Fig. 16 (before adjusting the natural frequencies). The numerical results here are consistent well with the evaluation above (Table 7).

Circumferential displacement and stresses in circumferential, radial and axial directions

Fig. 19 Responses with increasing natural frequencies and reducing 8th modal damping ratio to 0.075%

SUMMARY AND CONCLUSION

The nonsynchronous vibrations caused by unsteady tip clearance flow with considering the AMDRs of the key modes, which is obtained by the aerodynamic force due to blade vibration, are numerically investigated in a transonic rotor. The major conclusions are as follows:

- (1) The unsteady processes of TCF are similar at different operating conditions: radial vortexes caused by the unsteady TCF generate periodically in passage and propagate around circumference; at the same time, shedding vortexes periodically fall off the broken TCW and flow downstream along the blade tip pressure side. The radial vortexes impact on the tip leading edge of the following blade and cause high unsteady pressure amplitude here. The motion of shedding vortexes causes broad band unsteady pressure amplitude in the blade tip region. These two vortexes constitute the excitation source of NSV. Similar to flutter, but different from forced response, the excitation generates by the blades themselves and is nonsynchronous with the rotating speed.
- (2) With the mass flow reducing, the excitation frequency decreases gradually, but the amplitude increases. This is because the oscillating process is consisted of the propagation of radial vortexes in circumferential direction and shedding vortexes along flow direction. While the mass flow reduces, the shedding vortexes spend more time to flow downstream, what makes the oscillating period longer. With the rotating speed decreasing, the excitation becomes weak and even disappears due to the reduction of aerodynamic loading.
- (3) The responses of NSV are dominated by several modes, which is different from flutter that only one mode contributes to the vibration during flutter. With the operating condition changing, the dominant mode alters, which is decided by the modal shapes and the frequency differences between excitation and modes. According to the study in this paper, while NSV happens, the torsional and chord modes are easier to be excited. For the rotor here, the 7th, 8th and 9th modes are the dominant orders in most instances. The 7th modal shape (1st chordwise vibration) is much easier to be excited, and the 10th mode contributes rarely to the responses due to its high frequency and modal shape, even though it is much close to the excitation than 7th mode in some operation condition.
- (4) The responses are much larger in the upper part of the blade under different operating conditions and whatever the operating condition is, relative large vibration stresses always exist at the blade leading edge in tip region, which may cause high cycle fatigue. The radial stresses and circumferential stresses are the primary component, especially in tip region. The radial stresses are larger at about 70% to 80% blade spans and the largest circumferential stress appears at the tip of the

blade suction side. The maximal displacement locates at the leading edge of the blade tip.

- (5) The unsteady processes of TCF in every passage obtained from the seven passages model are similar to the results of single model, and are not affected by the vibration of blade. When the excitation is TCF, no phenomenon of locked-in is triggered, even though the frequencies of TCF and blade vibration are very close. The unsteady pressure amplitude of TCF keeps almost constant between different passages, but the unsteady pressure induced by intermediate blade vibration decays rapidly as the distance to intermediate blade increases. Therefore, only the middle three passages should be taken in consideration when calculate the AMDRs of higher-order modes.
- (6) The aerodynamic force of blade vibration is separated from that of TCF to calculate the AMDRs. The smallest AMDRs of 7th and 8th modes are 0.127% observed at 29th nodal diameter and 0.075% obtained at 8th nodal diameter, respectively. Rayleigh damping can only provide incremental modal damping ratios. If the damping is a key factor to the responses, Rayleigh damping condition is not sufficient, and the AMDRs should be considered.
- (7) The responses of the blade are determined by the damping and frequency differences between excitation and natural modes. While the frequency of excitation induced by TCW is far away from the natural frequencies, the AMDRs have little effect on the responses and the frequency differences supply a function of suppressing responses, which is much more effective than the AMDRs.
- (8) While the rotor works near the resonance, the responses are almost entirely contributed by the mode near the resonance. The amplitude enlarges much more significantly and the damping plays an important role in suppressing responses. For the blade in this paper, the domination modal order changes from 7th combining with 8th and 9th to only 8th, which modal frequency is adjusted to match the excitation frequency, and the maximum vibration stresses increase by four to ten times and five to eleven times with 0.1747% and 0.075% 8th modal damping ratio, respectively.

In additional, the excitation frequency can do match the natural frequency of 8th or 9th modes under a certain operating condition between Points 2 and 3 without adjusting the natural frequency, and if the resonant vibration stresses demands to be calculated accurately, besides the AMDR, the errors of the frequency should also be considered, as the responses are very sensitive to the frequency differences between the excitation and natural modes near the resonance condition.

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